

An Open-Source Prototype of Network Data Analytics Function for Next-Generation 5/6G Environments

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Abstract— The 5th Generation of mobile radio communication systems (5G) is paving the way to applications characterized by unprecedented performance levels. Thanks to technological paradigms such as Network Functions Virtualization (NFV) and microservices, applications and network services, including the 5G core itself, can be deployed where and when required across the cloud-edge continuum to deliver the proper Quality of Experience (QoE) to users on the move. Since deploying and scaling applications/network functions can cause a waste of network and computing resources and a growth of costs for network operators, specific tools are required to identify current resource demands to fulfil user needs while minimizing the footprint on the underlying hardware infrastructure. The Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF) was conceived for monitoring the edge and the cloud and producing Key Performance Indicators (KPI) accordingly, but actual implementations are still lacking. This paper presents the design and development of an NWDAF prototype to be integrated in the core of a 5G network, to provide useful data for the horizontal scaling of the cloud-native microservices composing the 5G core. Results show that the prototype causes negligible overheads on the overall 5G core performance, with CPU additional usages averaging 5.5%.

Keywords—5G, monitoring, open-source, NWDAF.

I. INTRODUCTION

The introduction of technologies related to the 5th Generation of mobile radio communication systems (5G) allows to support applications able to achieve performance levels never seen before [1]. Since such performance imposes strict constraints on the acceptable delays, it is essential to reduce the physical distance between the application and the user and to even follow users on the move. As a result, recent trends are shifting from monolithic applications and network services towards microservice-based applications [2] to improve their agility; this is consequently causing a shift from Virtual Machines (VMs) to container-based deployments.

In order to address such challenges, Network Functions Virtualization (NFV) [3] is seen as a key solution, to the point that the 5G Service-based Architecture (SBA) has been conceived with the design of the core functionalities as highly pluggable Network Functions (NFs) running in a virtual environment [4]. Using NFV, it is possible to transform physical network devices into sets of modular virtual functions that allow the entire 5G infrastructure to flexibly run on the cloud or edge computing resources.

This kind of technological approach enables network operators to avoid tailoring their services to specific special-purpose hardware, which is rarely upgraded because of costs and makes it hard to support and follow innovations in a timely manner. Through 5G and NFV, operators can rather use general purpose datacenter hardware, being free to add, modify, or remove an instance of any NFs and getting all the possible benefits of the cloud-edge continuum.

However, network operators must be very thorough with the amounts of computing and network resources that they consume to avoid an uncontrollable cost growth. For this reason, they need specific tools to understand the real demand for resources and ensure a good level of Quality of Experience (QoE), according to user needs and workloads, while minimizing the footprint on the underlying hardware infrastructure especially in moments of heavy load. This process is usually called horizontal scaling and it is one of the main advantages of cloud-native, microservice-based architectures with respect to monolithic ones.

As in standard cloud computing scenarios, the decision on the optimal number of function instances is a critical task that should be accomplished by maintaining a complete knowledge on the state of the network services and infrastructures: over-dimensioning clearly results in increased resources consumption and service costs; on the other side, under-dimensioning NFs might cause an overload of their instances, which can bring to bad levels of Quality of Service (QoS), and in the worst case, to even block the service.

To support the aforementioned decision process, 5G specifications include the definition of a radically new function, namely the Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF) [5], which has been specifically conceived to acquire monitored data at the edge and the cloud part of the infrastructure and to produce and analyze added-value Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), like forecasts of NF workloads, etc. While the presence of such a function would be crucial for the proper, real-time instantiation of NFs across the cloud-edge continuum, and similar solutions have been specified by several organizations [6], [7], to this day there is a lack of actual implementations available to the public.

In order to fill this gap, this paper presents the internal architecture design of a highly modular and expandable NWDAF, and the development of a preliminary prototype as an open-source project [8]. The prototype has been

interconnected with a working 5G environment to evaluate the performance and the quality of the undertaken approach. Results show that the overhead ascribable to the prototype is negligible and has no significant impact on the overall system performance.

The remaining of the paper is organized as follows. Section II introduces the NWDAF architecture, while its development is described in Section III. Validation and performance evaluation can be found in Section IV, while conclusions are drawn in Section V along with the future work.

II. NWDAF ARCHITECTURE

As outlined in the previous section, analytics are playing an increasingly relevant role as the network operators adopting 5G are heavily relying on the orchestration of microservice-based network functions and applications: the ability to deploy and scale instances on top of distributed facilities will be crucial to ensure the best user experience while keeping operations and capital costs under control. In this respect, 3GPP has specified the Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF) [5] as part of the 5G core to provide analytics at the edge and the cloud part of the infrastructure.

A. Main Concepts and Technologies

The softwarization revolution in telecommunication infrastructures that has seen NFV [3] and Edge Computing [9] as the main enabling technologies has paved the way to the current 5G specification. Virtualization allows to share high computational, storage and networking resources among different tenants; in particular, this provides both the aggregation of resources in central datacenters and the isolation among the different tenants.

Different layers of virtualization can be identified, which mainly differ from the type of resource offered in a virtualized form. Three main categories of virtualization can be identified: application layer virtualization, operating system virtualization (e.g., containerization), and hardware virtualization. Application layer virtualization, performed by means of Java Virtual Machines (JVMs), allows to run the same application over different operating systems and hardware. Operating system virtualization, the most relevant category for 5G, creates several isolated operating system environments through the use of containers. Every container shares the same system kernel and has its own files, users, processes and networks. Modular applications, usually called microservice applications, can be installed in their individual components over several, separated containers. Containers can also be instantiated, deleted or moved on demand and in an easy way. Finally, hardware virtualization emulates a device, of which every instance is a VM and reproduces the hardware through software emulation, or, by hardware support (Native and Para-virtualization).

While virtual machines have been widely used for the last ten years, and as such are extremely mature and well isolated, each application that is executed in a VM has to inherit the footprint of its base operating system and as such VMs are computationally heavier with respect to containers.

Containers are the main reason for having a modular core in 5G, because each functionality (NF) can be instantiated in a container making the most of the potential for virtualization. In fact, the usage of containers has been envisaged by 3GPP starting from the Release 15 specification: according to the

cloud-native application model, vertical applications and network services are realized through meshes of stateless (e.g., data are located externally to the microservices, linked on startup) microservices embedded into containers, supported by an orchestration layer that abstract the hardware in a homogeneous pool.

In this way, 5G networks can offer a number of features that can make a difference with respect to older generations of mobile networks: addition/removal of an instance at runtime (“horizontal scaling”), ease of application management, quick (re)deployment or even replacement in case of failure, just to name a few.

The 5G core itself is designed in a modular fashion, supporting cloud-native stateless NFs and separating User Plane (UP) functions from Control Plane (CP) ones. Each piece composing the core is a NF and offers services on the network through standardized service-based interfaces (on the control plane). Every NF can consume services offered by other NFs, even of the same type. The division between UP and CP allows independent scalability, deployment, and evolution. The microservice-based design allows to create different 5G networks on the same architecture (network slicing), which have a life of their own and, thanks to virtualization, can be totally isolated.

Another relevant feature is the presence of standardized API calls of NFs and the possibility for custom applications to access the 5G core to offer over-the-top services, new core functionalities, etc. In this way, everyone can develop a compatible module of the 5G system, which is what will be described in the following.

B. Structure of the NWDAF

The NWDAF collects data from other NFs and provides analytics services for automation or reporting. NFs can subscribe to the NWDAF to get notified about specific network status analytics and use such information to take decisions. In order to support decisions of NFV orchestrators (NFVOs), KPIs generated from the NWDAF can be used to enhance horizontal scaling mechanisms. This should help to offer services with a good QoE, while minimizing the footprint of the underlying infrastructure. This information lifecycle can be represented as in Figure 1: it is a closed-loop interaction, that, used correctly, allows the system to overcome user or traffic spikes, and, at the same time, help to enforce the Service Level Agreement (SLA).

While the 3GPP specification, along with similar ones from other working groups [6], recognizes the NWDAF as a

Figure 1. Closed-loop interaction between NWDAF, data producers (e.g., 5G core) and data consumers (e.g., NFVOs).

cornerstone for upcoming network management frameworks, at the time of writing, the available open-source 5G core releases do not provide a complete NWDAF. Therefore, this work aims to start filling this gap by proposing an NWDAF architecture and its implementation.

The proposed NWDAF architecture is shown in Figure 2. The *metric collector* module is in charge of retrieving information from the 5G core NFs by using an event-based notification mechanism: the *metric collector* can subscribe to an event of interest and receive a report upon changes on that event. It is also possible to choose a continuous event notification by setting a time periodicity for reports during the subscription process.

Once data have been retrieved from the NFs, they can be saved in the *storage* module or immediately sent to the *analytics* module to perform data processing. This latter module allows to plug in different algorithms depending on the desired KPIs. In fact, data analysis can encompass a large set of algorithms to be applied on time series data, among which forecasting is the most suitable for anticipating how the status of the system will evolve to support horizontal scaling mechanisms.

In the 5G context, it may be very useful to know how the load of the system will evolve in future hours, for example, how the trend of the used bandwidth will change in time, or how many devices will be connected to the system in few minutes. Predictions are made over sequential temporal data, or time series, that represent a quantity of interest. Since true values cannot be obtained by predictions, it is important to have an idea of how much forecasted data are reliable. A possible measure of the distance between observation and predictions can be the Mean Square Error (MSE), that can be computed directly on observed samples. Gathering continuously KPIs from the 5G core, through the *metric collector*, generates multiple time series on which predictions can be made. Different models can be used to forecast data, but some of them work better in certain situations, like when we have seasonal data. In the telecommunication context, for example, it usually happens that some KPIs have a daily pattern. For these reasons, in the evaluation presented in Section IV, the *analytics* provides a forecasting algorithm, namely, the Seasonal Auto-regressive Integrated Moving

Average (SARIMA [10]) model, whose goal is to predict future samples of a time series.

As shown in Figure 2, the *storage* module is receiving and storing data coming from the *metric collector* as well as the KPIs computed by the *analytics*, and it provides this information through REST API to other modules, even to external, third-party applications. This can be very useful for a network operator because it enables to visually inspect the status of the system, or other useful data, through custom visualization tools such as Grafana [11].

Moreover, KPIs generated from the *analytics* module can be very useful for supporting decisions of the NFVO to enhance horizontal scaling mechanisms. In fact, while the metrics usually consumed by NFVOs come from the infrastructure, data directly collected from NFs can for sure give a more precise and up-to-date view of the 5G core status and, as a result, help to offer services with a good QoE while minimizing the footprint of the underlying infrastructure. With specific reference to the forecasting feature, the obtained indicators can allow forecasting upcoming load/unload peaks and proactively change the number of instances for one or more NFs.

Finally, it is worth noting that, when using the event-based notifications, the frequency at which data are gathered depends on the event one, while for continuous event notification the selection of the notification frequency must be carefully pondered as it has an impact on the forecasting algorithm. The same holds true for data coming straight from the *metric collector* instead of the *storage*.

III. NWDAF SOFTWARE PROTOTYPE

The software prototype of the NWDAF has been developed to be part of the free5GC [12] open-source 5G core and follows the basic structure of the available NFs and their configuration files of that core release. The prototype is open-source as well and available at [8].

In more details, the NWDAF network function, which at the time of writing is not provided by free5GC, has been written with a modular, microservice-based structure whose components reflect the architectural models presented in Figure 2. Moreover, the prototype relies on additional open-source software and tools for testing purposes, such as UERANSIM [13] to simulate the presence of User Equipment (UEs) and gNodeBs.

As previously mentioned, the 5G core NFs can be deployed using containers according to a microservice-based approach, which improves the efficiency of scalability operations and the overall isolation of the prototype when deployed by multiple tenants. For the NWDAF modules, Docker was used to run every NF in a container and to create a virtual network connecting them. In this prototype, the modules most likely to be horizontally scaled are the *metric collector* and the *analytics*, for different reasons: while a single *metric collector* may not be enough depending on the data volume, for the *analytics* different forecasting algorithms may be required at the same time.

A. The Metric Collector Module

The *metric collector* module prototype is based on the 3GPP standardized APIs for the 5G core. Since this module is the one able to interact with the other NFs, it has been designed to also take care of additional, routine tasks that

Figure 2. The proposed architecture for the NWDAF.

require such interactions, such as registering to the Network Repository Function (NRF).

The behavior of the *metric collector* is described in Figure 3, which shows the interaction with the Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF) as an example. Firstly, it registers the NF itself at the NRF as an NWDAF. Afterwards, it opens and listens to the port 5000 on the specified interface reported in the configuration file and creates a new route corresponding to a GET request on `http://nwdaf-address:8000/metrics` where requests, generated from the *storage* module, are accepted.

When the initial configuration is successfully completed, the NWDAF asks to the NRF how many and which AMFs are connected to the core. A list of these NFs is kept locally and updated at the reception of a new request for metrics. Upon availability of this list, the software asks for a devices list in the Area Of Interest (AOI) at each AMF.

Once the device list has been provided, the *metric collector* can prepare a set of metrics corresponding to the number of devices connected at an AMF and the total number of devices on the network. Having a list of all devices in AOI, as shown in Figure 3, it can ask the relative AMF for the state of every device (registered, deregistered, connected, idle). Metrics on the devices state can be built accordingly and made available through a dedicated API. Finally, it is worth noting that the metric collector works with event-based APIs, but, since reports triggering is currently not supported in free5GC, data must be retrieved by polling the AMFs.

B. The Storage Module

The *storage* module, responsible for recording the actual metrics and making them available on time, consists of an installation of Prometheus [14] configured to target the data coming from the *metric collector*. Once Prometheus is up and storing metrics, a REST API allows to query the storage and retrieve temporal data for the forecasting algorithm, as well as for external consumption (see Figure 2).

Prometheus supports four types of metrics: (i) *counter* is a single monotonically increasing value. It can be reset to zero on restart, (ii) *gauge* is a single numerical value that can go up and down, (iii) *histogram* samples observations and counts them in customizable buckets, and (iv) *summary* samples observations in a similar manner to a histogram. It computes customizable quantiles over a sliding time window and offers a total count of observations and a sum of all observed values.

The metrics we are interested to collect are not cumulative and their values can grow and decrease. For this reason, the gauge type will be used for metrics collected and generated by the data collection module.

C. The Analytics Module

Once data have been stored, we can use the knowledge about past trends to build a forecasting model on the series. The *analytics* module has been designed to be as flexible as possible, in this way there is the possibility to switch the algorithm, with which the forecasting is done, in an easy way. The common way to access data, provided by Prometheus, offers this kind of flexibility and allows to retrieve a specific time series by just changing the name in the query. Moreover, thanks to the microservice structure of the prototype, it is possible to add multiple instances of the analytics module, so that different kinds of data can be elaborated depending on the behavior of the time series.

Since data are collected by Prometheus with a certain frequency, the same frequency can be used for the data fed to the forecasting algorithm. In the following it will be assumed that the collected time series has a daily seasonality with a growing mean value. The model fitting is done when enough recent samples are available, if there are not because the system has just been started, the software wait for them to be ready.

As previously mentioned, the software that was chosen for data visualization is Grafana. Once the software is running, it is possible to create custom dashboards that use, as data source, the Prometheus instance. Each plot/graph generated by Grafana is connected to at least one of the metrics available in the storage and shows its behavior over time. An example of dashboard is depicted in Figure 4: in this case, each sample is taken every 10 seconds with a seasonal frequency of 24 samples. Grafana also has the capability to generate alerts for system administrators/ tenants.

IV. VALIDATION AND PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

The following subsection aim to assess the soundness of the developed NWDAF prototype (Section IV.A) and to evaluate its impact on the overall performance of the 5G core (Section IV.B). The entire system is deployed using Docker Compose to automate the installation and configuration of modules and allow for an easy and fast deployment of the system, as well as the possibility to update a single module

Figure 3. Interaction between the NWDAF *metric collector* module and the AMF.

Figure 4. A view from the Grafana dashboard.

with just one command line. A container is created for each of the modules composing the prototype, as well as for the Grafana data visualization tool, the simulated gNodeB, the simulated UEs and for each NF implemented in free5GC. Two additional containers using cAdvisor [15] are deployed for performance monitoring.

A. Validation of the Developed NWDAF Modules

This subsection is dedicated to testing the correct behavior of the whole developed software. The validation is performed on the AMFs: a script has been written to simulate the automated connection and disconnection of devices in UERANSIM, and the Prometheus web interface is used to look at the stored data and comparing them with the values from the log of the device simulation.

In more details, UERANSIM simulates UEs and gNodeBs registering and deregister to/from the 5G core and to instantiate PDU sessions. During simulations, one gNodeB was in place along with a varying the number of UEs connected to the network. Having more than one UE to simulate means a configuration file for each UE, so a python script has been developed to duplicate a starting UE configuration file by changing just the International Mobile Subscriber Identity (IMSI) and the International Mobile Equipment Identity (IMEI) in the copies. After the configuration files have been created and the duplicated devices have been added to the allowed list of the core, an additional script is used to simulate devices connection: at each step, a Gaussian random variable with given mean and standard deviation, changing at every iteration, is sampled. The obtained value from the random process represents the number of connected devices. Once the software has sampled this value, it adds/removes UE instances to reach the desired number of devices. The time interval with which the random variable is sampled, is configurable, in terms of mean values, of the random process, to be provided to the algorithm and create the desired distribution over time. Mean values and standard deviations defining the random process repeat after m samples, m being the season duration, this creates the seasonality of device numbers over time. The validation consists in checking whether the data collected on the number of connected devices correspond to the forecasted one.

The MSE was used to evaluate the difference between the real observed values and the predictions. As depicted in Table 1, for a total number of fitting samples limited to 336, the MSE between the predicted and the measured data satisfactorily stays around 3.5.

B. Performance Evaluation

In order to evaluate the impact of the proposed prototype on the overall performance of the 5G core, the usage times of the CPU for each NF is calculated, in its mean values, in the presence and absence of the NWDAF, along with those of the modules composing the NWDAF itself. Every experiment has been repeated 20 times and has the duration of one hour; results are reported in Table 2.

We can notice that the *metric collector* module is not computationally heavy with respect to the AMF or the SMF. The *analytics* has a higher resource consumption, but this could be reduced by selecting a more efficient forecasting algorithm. The *storage* and the visualization tool are not so relevant in performance terms.

Table 1. MSE of the simulated number of connected devices against the forecasted one.

#samples	#real	#forecasted	MSE
330	12	14.18689	3.61207
331	14	13.60512	3.59873
332	13	14.20655	3.590493
333	17	16.48690	3.57774
334	15	15.964836	3.56764
335	15	14.75925	3.55429
336	12	11.55593	3.54158

Table 2. CPU usage time for the 5G core NFs. * indicates measurements obtained in the absence of the NWDAF (e.g., last three lines of the table.)

NF	Avg Time [s]	Avg Time* [s]	Difference [%]
UDR	10.61	9.83	7.36
NRF	11.20	10.84	3.21
PCF	4.84	4.30	11.16
UPF	3.23	2.80	12.07
AMF	20.57	19.58	4.82
AUSF	3.27	3.16	3.37
UDF	10.80	10.77	0.27
NSSF	0.73	0.70	4.40
SMF	11.39	11.14	2.20
<i>metric collector</i>	2.68		
<i>storage</i>	2.58		
<i>analytics</i>	19.42		
			5.42

When the NWDAF is turned off, we can see that the impact on the 5G core is not relevant at all, with values in the two columns being almost the same: on average, as reported in the bottom right of the table, the overhead is below 5.5%. We can conclude the performance evaluation saying that the software prototype implementation of NWDAF impact on the system is within expectation, not weighing heavily on system performance.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This paper has presented the design and development of a Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF) to be integrated in the core of a 5G network. The objectives of data collection and subsequent processing, originally defined by 3GPP specifications for NWDAF, have been expanded to provide useful data for the horizontal scaling of the cloud-native microservices composing the 5G core.

A prototype software implementation of the NWDAF has been conceived and developed in a modular form, to fully reap the benefits of the cloud-edge continuum and open up to the development of further modules, even outside the intended purposes of the proposed forecasting one.

The *metric collector* and the *storage* modules have been tested in their operation, showing that is possible to obtain useful data from the core. Then, for the *analytics*, a script capable of simulating devices has been used to emulate the distribution of connected devices on which forecasting is done as well as the lifecycle of the UEs. The code for every module has been provided as open-source, in this way it can be reused, enhanced and extended as desired.

The prototype validation displays a small MSE between the measured data and the forecasting ones; moreover, measures on the CPU used in presence or absence of the proposed NWDAF show that its impact on the other core NFs is negligible and the usage of the NWDAF modules themselves provides similar performance. While the *analytics*

module uses slightly more CPU, it is worth noting that algorithms are pluggable thanks to the way the prototype has been designed and, in the future, a better performing algorithm can be selected for the forecasting.

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